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Diffusion inspired training strategy for Source Separation in the frequency domain

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Let's go!

Santi

Abstract

ENGLISH - The challenge of segregating individual musical components from a compound auditory signal is a longstanding issue in the realm of audio processing. Classical methodologies have provided quite interesting solutions but presenting limitations in robustness. Drawing inspiration from the recent success and popularity of diffusion models, this work hypothesizes that such training strategy, combined with a frequency-domain-based implementation, can offer substantial improvements in the task of music source separation. The leading-edge implementations of this topic hinge on conventional architectures such as U-net or Wave-U-Net and training approaches with little novelty. This means that the few improvements that can be achieved depend on the amount of data available and the depth of the neural network. This thesis approaches the problem from a different perspective, proposing a novel training strategy based on the nature of diffusion models. To this end, we will first approach the creation from scratch of a music source separation model with different variants and then apply the novel training strategy. The significance of this research lies not just in advancing the technical capabilities of music source separation, but also in the potential applications in areas such as music remixing, restoration, or automatic music transcription. This thesis, therefore, serves as a vanguard, encouraging further exploration and refinement in the domain of music source separation applying a diffusion-inspired training strategy.

Keywords: Music source separation, diffusion models, frequency domain.

CATALÀ - El repte de segregar components musicals individuals d'un senyal auditiu compost és un problema de llarga data en l'àmbit del processament d'àudio. Les metodologies clàssiques han proporcionat solucions força interessants però presentant limitacions en la robustesa. Inspirant-se en l'èxit recent i la popularitat dels models de difusió, aquest treball planteja la hipòtesi que aquesta estratègia d'entrenament, combinada amb una implementació basada en el domini de la freqüència, pot oferir millores substancials en la tasca de separació de fonts musicals. Les implementacions d'avantguarda d'aquest tema es basen en arquitectures convencionals com ara U-net o Wave-U-Net i enfocaments d'entrenament amb poca novetat. Això vol dir que les poques millores que es poden aconseguir depenen de la quantitat de dades disponibles i de la profunditat de la xarxa neuronal. Aquesta tesi aborda el problema des d'una perspectiva diferent, proposant una nova estratègia formativa basada en la naturalesa dels models de difusió. Amb aquest objectiu, primer abordarem la creació des de zero d'un model de separació de fonts musicals amb diferents variants i després aplicarem la nova estratègia d'entrenament. La importància d'aquesta investigació no rau només en l'avenç de les capacitats tècniques de la separació de fonts musicals, sinó també en les aplicacions potencials en àrees com la remixes musicals, la restauració o la transcripció automàtica de música. Aquesta tesi, per tant, serveix d'avantguarda, fomentant una exploració i perfeccionament posteriors en el domini de la separació de fonts musicals aplicant una estratègia de formació inspirada en la difusió.

Paraules clau: Separació de fonts musicals, models de difusió, domini de freqüència.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

The field of digital signal processing, and more specifically, audio signal processing, has received great importance in recent years, with the study of different areas related to the perception of music and speech by humans. More specifically in music, the Music Information Retrieval expansion, more intense since the appearance of the ISMIR conference in the year 2000, has allowed the intensive study of certain aspects such as music classification [1], music recommender systems [2], music source separation or instrument recognition [3], automatic music transcription [4], among others. The main object of this thesis is the study of different strategies for one of the most studied problems in the field, Music Source Separation.

Source Separation is the science of automatically separating signals or sources from a main mixture. These signals to be separated can be of different types: multi-speaker source separation, where the signals of 2 or more participants in a speech or dialogue are separated [5]; speech enhancement, where the voice of a speaker is separated in an original audio that contains appreciable background noise [6]; or as is the subject of this thesis, Music Source Separation, which by nature also has different variants; blind music source separation (it is not known in advance which sources there are), instrument isolation or, as will be seen in this document, source separation with prior knowledge of which sources are separated.

The first publications related to this phenomenon occur in the 1990s, where the

study of different techniques based on traditional signal processing can be observed [7], [8], [9]. They are mainly published in signal processing reference journals and conferences such as *IEEE Signal Processing Magazine* or *International Conference of HF Radio Systems and Techniques*, among others. In these cases, the studies had a very evident mathematical component, where the type of signal was not the determining factor of each paper. In the aforementioned references, we can observe the study of separation techniques for mixing signals with background noise, without background noise or the study of the cocktail party effect [10], among others. In none of the cases is a signal of a musical nature mentioned.

It was not until the appearance of the aforementioned ISMIR conference that studies of this kind began to appear, focusing on the type of signal of a musical nature, and therefore applying specific techniques for this type of signal that for multi-speaker separation or speech enhancement would perhaps not be so applicable. [11], [12].

From this point onwards, the field of source separation has been extensively studied. Techniques from the different variants of source separation previously discussed have been combined, tested for different types of signals, and so on. It is in the first half of the 2010s that proposals for Music Source Separation using deep learning approaches began to appear. The first versions of this phenomenon applied the widely known RNN (Recurrent Neural Networks) [13], until the appearance of dedicated architectures in 2016 and 2017 such as U-net [14] or Wave-U-Net [15], among others. In the next section of this thesis, "State of the art", we will go more into detail on what architectures and approaches are being used nowadays.

It must be noted that, since studies regarding Music Source Separation became more and more common, some evaluation campaigns have been carried out, encouraging researchers to build better systems. Some examples of these events can be Music Information Retrieval Evaluation eXchange (MIREX) [16], Signal Separation Evaluation Campaign (SISEC) [17] (where MUSDB18 was created) and the most recent one, Music Demixing Challenge [18] organized from 2021 onwards, in where the state-of-the-art approaches of Music Source Separation have been presented in 2021 and 2022.

At this point, it is time to ask what are the main applications of music source separation; for what purpose is so much effort devoted to it. Quoting from the tutorial published by ISMIR in 2020, “There are many reasons to study source separation. One might be interested in using existing methods to enhance a downstream task, or one might be interested in source separation as a pursuit itself”. This quote is key to defining the applications of Music Source Separation, as it divides them into two clear camps. The very first one, and maybe the most common, in which MSS is used to enhance a downstream task, some clear applications can be mentioned: automatic music transcription [19], lyrics and music alignment [20], vocal activity detection [21], f_0 estimation [22], among others. When talking about “Music Source Separation as a pursuit itself”, it refers to the applications in which the extracted source can be used not to accomplish another task, but in itself; automatic karaoke (isolate the accompaniment information of a song), tasks related to music production, in where sometimes a concrete source of a song might be used for some creative applications within this field, among others.

1.1 Motivation

In this thesis, we focus on Music Source Separation (MSS) for a four-stem instrument arrangement. It must be noted that this approach is the most common in the field. The vast majority of papers regarding MSS focus on designing a system that can separate high-quality signals of vocals, drums, bass and others for a given mixture that contains those four sources. More concretely, vocal source separation is more studied than “bass SS” or “drums SS”, because of its possible applications. It should be also mentioned that the harmonic and complex nature of the vocal signal allows a big amount of approaches to work better over it than over other kinds of sources.

There exist several other combinations of sources that have been studied, such as orchestral music, choral music (SATB) or even other musical traditions, in which “non-western” instruments can be found [23] .

There exists a profound bias in MSS systems in this matter, because the main focus

has been put in four-stem approaches, so they don't work for other genres of cultural music traditions as good as they do for this common approach.

In this thesis, although we are aware of that situation, we will be proposing a diffusion frequency-based system trained with **MUSDB18** [24], the most common four-stem dataset, as we know that the simplicity that this approach gives permits to test novel proposals and see whether there are worth or not, and then expand them to another data.

In recent years, different state-of-the-art approaches have been presented. We will focus in detail on them in the next section. Nevertheless, to the best of our knowledge, there is only one paper that has tried to implement what can be known as *Cold Diffusion* for a Source Separation problem [25] [26], and it corresponds to the supervisor and co-supervisor of this thesis.

Briefly, and in order to understand the context, *Cold Diffusion* is a variation of the well-known diffusion models. Standard diffusion models involve an image transform adding Gaussian noise and an image restoration operator that inverts the previous degradation (further explanation in section 3). However, *Cold Diffusion* has been created from the observation that the generative behavior of diffusion models is not strongly dependent on the choice of image degradation, so that is why Gaussian Noise is not the only option. Therefore, the *Cold Diffusion* method relies on a deterministic degradation, which in this particular case is the mixture signal itself.

In the paper commented just before this clarification, which we will take as reference for this document, a waveform-based SS system was presented, and a diffusion-inspired “training strategy” was implemented. Plaja et al. in [27] were able to confirm that this training strategy has benefits regarding subjective perception of the extracted vocal source, being comparable to state-of-the-art approaches such as Demucs [28]. Having those results, they proposed some future works that are the object of this thesis.

1.2 Objectives

It must be noted that waveform-based SS systems are quite important in the field, but there is another branch which could be considered even more common and used: spectrogram-based SS systems. Quoting Plaja et al. in [27], “We also look at extending the approach, for instance, by using a different or improved network to learn the reverse process, focusing on U-Nets which are the leading architecture music source separation.”

That is the reason for this thesis; the extension of the implementation of the reference paper, which contains two objectives that are consequent to each other and that the second could not be achieved without first achieving the first:

- 1. Construction from scratch of a Source Separation system based on the frequency domain, achieving an architecture that allows quality results to be achieved on an objective and subjective level.**
- 2. Once this system is achieved, application of the diffusion models with the cold diffusion method to the final architecture and achieve subjective metrics and analysis comparable to the performance of the Unet without diffusion and the waveform-based diffusion implementation of the reference paper.**

If both objectives are achieved, conclusions of great importance to the field of source separation research can be drawn; it would demonstrate that one of the most widespread architectures in the field has a training strategy that can achieve better metrics both objectively and perceptually; it would also justify that the work done by in [27] can be generalized for more Source Separation implementations, encouraging researchers to investigate this training strategy in detail for other architectures or combine it with other mechanisms used in Source Separation such as conditioning.

1.3 Structure of the thesis

This thesis has been divided in some sections that are detailed here. First, you will find the State of the art chapter, in which we will explain in detail the current situation of the matter, pointing on the different techniques and architectures that are the current best implementations. After, you can find the Implementation chapter. Here we explain the details regarding the different architectures that have been used and we also explain how diffusion models work and have been implemented in this algorithm.

Afterwards the training process can be found. Here you will find the different techniques and strategies that have been used for training the neural network. The evaluation chapter comes after this one, in which we explain which results we got from our experiments. Conclusions is the final chapter, in which you can find conclusions and further works regarding the whole master thesis.

For accessing the code regarding the master thesis, please do not hesitate to contact the author.

Chapter 2

State of the art

In order to understand the current situation of Source Separation, in this chapter a summary of the state of the art techniques will be presented. It must be considered that this thesis has different aspects of which an individual state of the art analysis could be held, such as Source Separation itself or Diffusion Models. That is why the development of this section will go through all these areas, presenting which is the current state of them, and justifying the research being carried out in this thesis.

2.1 Source Separation

Music Source Separation is the task of isolating individual sounds in an auditory mixture of multiple sounds. During the last years there have been several studies dealing with this technique, proposing different approaches and data collections. The interest of separating sources from a mixture is quite interesting when talking about industrial applications in streaming services or platforms that deal with music, enhancing automatic music transcription [29], musical instrument detection [30], lyric recognition [31], fundamental frequency estimation [32], among others.

The latest and most promising approaches in Source Separation are approached from two different domains: frequency and time. It is not possible to state categorically that one is better than the other, due to both the results and the artifacts produced

are perceptually different and subjective. Both appeared in a similar time frame, with the publication of their presentation papers [14] and [15].

When we refer to the way in which the Source Separation model is approached, we really mean the neural network architecture that is being trained to achieve the goal. As can be seen from the above references, both domains appeared more or less at the same time, although the time-domain architecture approach is a simplification of dimensions of the original frequency-domain architecture. Therefore, the commonly used Wave-U-Net in the time-domain [15] with one dimension less in the convolutions. Note that the architecture used in this thesis will be explained in more detail below.

Figure 1: Music Source Separation

Since the Wave-U-Net paper appeared in 2018, time-domain representations have been used more and more progressively from one point of view or another. Projects such as Conv-Tas-Net [33], MTG [34] or Demucs [28]. The latter project was, at the time of its publication, the state of the art as far as Source Separation was concerned. It showed that mastering time can offer promising results. In fact, it should be noted that the paper in which this thesis is framed, presented by Genís Plaja, Marius Miron and Xavier Serra at ISMIR 2022, implements a Source Separation system in the time domain, and achieves quite acceptable metrics and subjective perception [27].

On the other hand, the frequency version appeared a few years earlier and was the basis for the subsequent implementation over time. This architecture, the U-net, appeared in 2015 [14] in image segmentation applications. As can be imagined,

the application to the field of audio source separation happened in 2017, when it was observed that the image segmentation that two years earlier had been performed using the U-net, could now be used on a two-dimensional representation of an audio, i.e. on its spectrogram [35]

Since that time, this architecture has been the undisputedly the most widely used when it comes to Source Separation applied in the frequency domain. When we refer to the frequency domain, we must introduce as output to the network the audio in two dimensions, that is to say, in the form of a spectrogram. This is the input that the U-net receives, and therefore the architecture is typical of a convolutional neural network with two-dimensional convolutional layers. Therefore, from 2017 to the present, different approaches utilizing U-net architecture have not only appeared, but also represented the state-of-the-art when measuring the results with Source Separation metrics that will also be explained in much more detail in future sections.

The frequency based source separation is typically done using a time-frequency mask, which, in its simplest form, is defined as the gain between (0) and (1) to apply on each element of the time-frequency representation of the mixture (e.g., an STFT) in order to estimate the desired signal. After multiplication of the mixture by a mask, the separated signal is recovered through an inverse time-frequency transform [36]. This concept will also be detailed in future sections.

A few examples of them could be DenseNet [37] or Spleeter [38]. Nevertheless, it can be seen that domain combined representations are also presented, and they perform state of the art Source Separation. A well-known example, and current state of the art is Demucs [39], with its new implementation using transformers [40]. As they explain in their paper, “In this work, we show how to perform end-to-end hybrid source separation, letting the model decide which domain is best suited for each source, and even combining both”. It is clear then that deciding one of the two domains makes no sense, because both, either combined or alone, have performed state-of-the-art in Music Source Separation.

Having this in mind, one of the first steps of this thesis is to transform the model implemented by Plaja [27] to the frequency domain, as we believe that we have taken benefit from the time-domain implementation as much as it could be taken, and possibly the frequency domain can offer another view that produces better results in this concrete case. (I suppose that in the introduction I will explain in more detail my supervisor’s paper, so that’s why I don’t explain it more deeply in this section).

2.2 Diffusion models

As it was mentioned in the introduction, the starting point of this thesis is the paper published by its supervisor. It makes use of a training strategy based on diffusion models. In this section we will explain in detail the current state of the art regarding diffusion models, why they are so important in current Deep Learning and why they are used throughout this thesis.

The origin of diffusion models dates back to 2015, with the publication of the paper “Deep Unsupervised Learning using Nonequilibrium Thermodynamics” [41]. As it can be read in the title, this paper presented diffusion models inspired by non-equilibrium statistical physics. They present a new way to “systematically and slowly destroy structure in a data distribution through an iterative forward diffusion process and then learn a reverse process that restores structure in data, yielding a highly flexible and tractable generative model of the data”. The community had to wait until December 2020 for the publication by UC Berkeley of “Denoising Diffusion Probabilistic Models” [42] to see diffusion models applied to an image synthesis task, outperforming generative techniques such as Variational Autoencoders or Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs). In the figure 2 you can find some of those models explained graphically.

Since then, diffusion models have become a standard in Generative Artificial Intelligence, achieving state-of-the-art performances in image [43] or music generation [44], among others. In later sections of this thesis, diffusion models will be explained

Figure 2: Generative Adversarial Networks, Variational Autoencoders and Flow-based generative models.

in depth, going through everything that has to do with their mathematics.

Working with audio or music using diffusion models is becoming more and more common, with tasks such as music synthesis [45], speech enhancement [6], symbolic music generation [46], text-conditioned music generation [44] or [47] among others. It may be noted that lots of diffusion based generations are also conditioned with different variables depending on the domain. There are quite broadly known implementations of text-based image synthesis [43] or text-based audio synthesis as mentioned above [47].

Bearing in mind the impact that diffusion models are having in the field of deep learning in recent years, this thesis uses a training strategy for Source Separation models based on diffusion models. Again, we cite the paper on which this project is based [27], where this concept, which other authors have dubbed "cold diffusion", was devised. As a general and brief idea, diffusion is based on image transformation adding an stochastic distribution through a finite number of steps. In papers such as [25] or [26], as well as the one by this thesis supervisor, the idea of varying the choice of the "image degradation" (use a deterministic signal instead of a stochastic signal) has been researched with interesting results. In these references, demonstrated conclusions say that even using completely deterministic degradations, the training and testing can be easily generalized to create generative models.

The idea of Cold Diffusion is the base of the implementation of this thesis, due to the signal that is used for “image” degradation of the source that we want to extract is the mixture signal, which is undoubtedly a deterministic distribution. Further explanation of this concept will be explained in the diffusion models section of this thesis.

Chapter 3

Implementation

As has been explained in both sections 1 and 2, the architecture used in this thesis is based on the predefined and widely used **Unet architecture**. Unet was introduced in 2015 as a solution for segmentation in biomedical imaging [14]. However, it was not until 2017 when Jansson. et al in [35] proposed Unet as a solution for a Source Separation problem. Since then, architecture has become increasingly popular and is now the means of arriving at algorithms that represent the state of the art.

3.1 U-net architecture

The goal of the neural network is to predict the components of the source being separated from the mixture that is given as input. The output of the final decoder layer is a soft mask that is multiplied element-wise with the mixed spectrogram to obtain the final estimate.

Unet can be explained as an encoder-decoder architecture. Quoting [14], “The main idea is to supplement a usual contracting network by successive layers, where pooling operators are replaced by upsampling operators”. As it can be seen Figure in 4, Unet is divided in 3 parts: encoder, bottleneck and decoder.

First, the main goal of the encoder is to reduce the input image to a **latent space** in which the image size is highly reduced, but the number of channels is increased by

Figure 3: **Left:** mixture signal. **Middle:** unet-generated mask. **Right:** output signal. Result of multiplying mixture and mask

two in each encoder block, performing the contextual feature extraction effectively. The usual representation of each block of the decoder is a convolutional block. A convolutional block is basically constructed by a convolutional layer that takes as input a fixed block input channels and outputs the next element of the vector of features, which is standardized to twice the input channels. The convolutional layer is usually followed by a normalization layer, in which the feature maps created by the previous layer are normalized. This normalization step aims to improve the stability, convergence and generalization of the block during both training and inference. One common technique used in this state is batch normalization, although different techniques can be found around the literature [48]. Finally comes the activation function, which can be of different types, depending on the way the network is implemented; for example, SiLU or ReLU.

This function introduces the non-linearity to the network, essential to be able to learn complex relationships, enable gradient flow and make the model expressive. The last step before the next block of the decoder is the downsampling operation, to reduce the dimensions of the feature maps. This operation can be done in several ways, although a common way to do it is to apply the MaxPooling operation.

Once achieved that latent space, the feature maps arrive at the **bottleneck**. This module just implements two convolutional blocks (the same block as in the encoder) to give stability to the features obtained during the downsampling process, and pre-

Figure 4: Unet architecture

prepares them for the decoding part. After the bottleneck, the feature maps get to the final part of the network, in which they will be transformed to the input dimensions by performing **upsampling** operations, as the previous quote mentioned.

The goal of the decoder is to give meaning to the features obtained during the encoding layers, and transform them into a mask that can be multiplied to the input to obtain the desired output. The usual way to perform the decoding operation is to apply a symmetric network to the encoder but switching the input and output channels in a reversed way, going from bottleneck channels to output channels. It also switches the downsampling operation of the encoder by an upsampling operation.

A detail that must be taken into account is the addition of what is called the **skip connection**. As it can be seen in the Figure 4, each decoder block takes as input a skip connection that comes from the equivalent level in the encoder. Just before the downsampling operation in the encoder, the feature map is taken and it is concatenated in the channel dimension to the input of the corresponding decoding block, doubling the number of channels in each decoder block compared to the equivalent encoder block.

This addition ensures that low-level information flows directly from the high-resolution

input to the high-resolution output. It can be seen as "giving context to the decoder to perform its task having more information", and therefore better.

The very last step of the network is to create the mask that then will be multiplied to the input to obtain the desired source separated, as it is shown in Figure 3. To generate the mask, a sigmoid function is applied to the output of the last block of the decoder, which will give values between 0 and 1 to the output spectrogram because of the nature of the sigmoid function. Sigmoid function is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Sigmoid function.

This implementation that has been just explained is a **Vanilla Unet**, that will be implemented in this thesis as a first stage. After that, and depending on some variables such as the goal of the network or the data available, the Vanilla Unet is extended with more layers or more depth in feature maps. That is the second step taken in the implementation of this thesis, that is explained in the next section.

3.2 Vanilla U-net and Res-Unet

As it has been explained just before, the first goal of the thesis was to create a “Vanilla U-net” from scratch. This decision was taken because of two main reasons:

1. Construct the project step by step being able to achieve at least reasonable results during the process. That has been considered a good practice in the development of this project due to the complexity of creating those networks from scratch.
2. Having intermediate results during the whole process makes it easier to change some configuration or parameters. This reason was considered before starting the whole implementation.

Once achieved both the architecture and the results, the next goal of this thesis was to create a better Source Separation system that could at least be compared in some way to the ones representing the state-of-the-art. For that purpose, Res-Unet has been implemented. As it will be detailed in the evaluation section, we have been able to accomplish better results than Vanilla U-net, achieving the first objective of the thesis commented in the previous sections.

It should be noted that the other objective of the thesis is to implement a “diffusion inspired” training strategy for Source Separation. It was considered that, for that purpose, there was a need to build a “comparable to the state-of-the-art” network to test whether diffusion works or not. Also, as it has been said before, one of the reference papers of this thesis [27] used that training strategy over a state-of-the-art implementation based in the waveform domain. So, if we hadn’t a comparable network behind the process, the comparison with that paper wouldn’t be fair.

3.2.1 Res-Unet architecture

The architecture of the Res U-net isn’t that different from the Vanilla U-net, but it contains a huge number of layers in comparison to the Vanilla one, so the implementation is not trivial.

Figure 6: Unet architecture in 3D.

You can imagine an architecture such as the Figure 6, with the same encoder-bottleneck-decoder form, but the blocks are bigger. It is inspired in this paper [49].

The main block of the network will be called **RCB**. That block contains similar elements to the Vanilla implementation, but not exactly in the same order. The RCB is a convolutional block that contains the next layers in order: "BatchNorm2d", "LeakyReLU", "Conv2d", "BatchNorm2d", "LeakyReLU" and "Conv2d".

It must be noted that channels are changed in the first convolutional layer from “input channels” to the double, that will be the “output channels” of the block. The main difference comes now, because each encoder and decoder blocks contain 4 RCB blocks. That supposes the addition of a big number of parameters to the network, which makes it more capable of doing the task of source separation if good data is used to train it.

As a summary, the encoder/decoder block contains 6 blocks of 4 RCB. Each RCB contains 2 convolutional layers, so the both the encoder and the decoder contain 48 layers. The bottleneck contains 4 more RCB blocks, which adds 8 more convolutional layers. The whole network consists of **104 convolutional layers**, which finally means over **150.000.000 parameters**. That number of parameters can be

considered a big network for the task of Music Source Separation. As a comparison, Vanilla U-net contains only 26 layers, so the Res U-net is 4 times bigger in both number of layers and number of parameters.

100 hours of training data seems enough for this network not to overfit. Overfitting is a problem that can be suffered in different situations. One of them is having a huge network with a small amount of data, which leads to a literal learning of that training data. The result of this phenomenon would be that the network would not be able to separate anything that hadn't seen before, and we thought that it might happen with this network. Nevertheless, it hasn't happened, so we are proud to have built such as big network without suffering that problem.

3.3 Diffusion models theory

Quoting myself in the previous sections, “once the Source Separation system is achieved, we will apply diffusion models with the cold diffusion method to the final architecture”. To make it easy to understand how diffusion models will work with the Source Separation system, we will dedicate this section to explain them with detail. After that, we will explain how we use them for Source Separation concretely.

As we explained in the State of the Art, diffusion models became widely used with the presentation in December 2020 of the paper “Denoising Diffusion Probabilistic Models”. That paper introduces mainly the diffusion models theory, although it also shows some applications related to image generation.

There is a first assumption that must be understood: diffusion models are **generative** models. That means that they are meant to create new data from previously seen data. Let's say we have a thousand images of dogs in our dataset. The objective of the diffusion process over that corpus would be to create an image of a dog that is not contained in that dataset. Other widely known generative implementations such as GANs (Generative Adversarial Networks), autoregressive models or VAEs (Variational Autoencoders) have been outperformed in a lot of applications regarding image, sound, text generation, among others.

“A diffusion probabilistic model is a parameterized Markov chain trained using variational inference to produce samples matching training data. Transitions of this chain are learned to reverse the diffusion process.”

Let’s start by explaining it in a very simple way. The purpose is to generate new data. The diffusion process works by applying **noise** to the training data step by step and learning how to reverse that process, so that is the model can generate new data samples from a given noise distribution. The mathematics behind that process are quite complex to give an in-depth analysis in this report, but we will try to make them a bit clearer to understand all the process. See Figure 7 for understanding what we are talking about.

Efficient training is therefore possible by optimizing random terms of L with stochastic gradient descent. Further improvements come from variance reduction by rewriting L (3) as:

$$\mathbb{E}_q \left[\underbrace{D_{\text{KL}}(q(\mathbf{x}_T|\mathbf{x}_0) \parallel p(\mathbf{x}_T))}_{L_T} + \sum_{t>1} \underbrace{D_{\text{KL}}(q(\mathbf{x}_{t-1}|\mathbf{x}_t, \mathbf{x}_0) \parallel p_\theta(\mathbf{x}_{t-1}|\mathbf{x}_t))}_{L_{t-1}} - \underbrace{\log p_\theta(\mathbf{x}_0|\mathbf{x}_1)}_{L_0} \right] \quad (5)$$

(See Appendix A for details. The labels on the terms are used in Section 3.) Equation (5) uses KL divergence to directly compare $p_\theta(\mathbf{x}_{t-1}|\mathbf{x}_t)$ against forward process posteriors, which are tractable when conditioned on $\mathbf{x}_0$:

$$q(\mathbf{x}_{t-1}|\mathbf{x}_t, \mathbf{x}_0) = \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{x}_{t-1}; \tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_t(\mathbf{x}_t, \mathbf{x}_0), \tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_t \mathbf{I}), \quad (6)$$

$$\text{where } \tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_t(\mathbf{x}_t, \mathbf{x}_0) := \frac{\sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_{t-1}}\beta_t}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_t} \mathbf{x}_0 + \frac{\sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_t}(1 - \bar{\alpha}_{t-1})}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_t} \mathbf{x}_t \quad \text{and} \quad \tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_t := \frac{1 - \bar{\alpha}_{t-1}}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_t} \beta_t \quad (7)$$

Consequently, all KL divergences in Eq. (5) are comparisons between Gaussians, so they can be calculated in a Rao-Blackwellized fashion with closed form expressions instead of high variance Monte Carlo estimates.

Figure 7: Diffusion mathematics

As we explained before, the process is the following:

1. We have a data sample from our training data. The process starts by adding a noise distribution (standardly gaussian) step by step. As it can be seen in the Figure 8, the image starts getting blurred step by step until it is a fully noised image.

Figure 8: Forward and reverse diffusion

2. The diffusion process is always aware of the step in which is located, so it can depend only on the previous one. That is the basic idea of a Markov Chain. The ultimate objective of the process is to be able to reconstruct that addition of noise giving a noisy image as input. Here is where the neural network comes and tries to accomplish that work.

Figure 9: Diffusion reverse process.

3. The network, which is a U-net architecture in the original implementation, uses the forward process as data for training. The training process shows the network how the distribution in each step is, so it learns how to make that process happen in the reversed way. This process can be seen as an iterative refinement of the latent variable, which is the noised image, to convert it to a new data sample.

Details regarding variables can be found in the original paper, but for this thesis a very important one must be introduced: **noise schedule**. The noise schedule is the level of perturbation in each diffusion step. We must be aware of this variable because it will be manipulated after in the training process, and the reader must know what it is. As [27] note in their paper, choosing the noise schedule has found to be crucial to the performance of diffusion models. The standard scenario is to use a pre-defined distribution that has linear addition of noise along steps.

Another parameter that must be considered is the **amount of diffusion steps**. There is still a lot of research regarding this matter, because it usually depends on the task being performed. It has been found that for audio, 20 is a reliable option. That means that noise will be added in 20 steps from the completely clean image to the completely noised image. This decision depends on different considerations, such as learning process itself or latency at inference stage. It should be noted that the more steps the longer inference, so a compromise must be found between those variables.

The application of diffusion models has been found effective in several applications such as: image generation, music generation, speech generation and enhancement, text generation, text-conditioned music and image generation, among others. After the presentation of some of the reference papers of this master thesis [27],[25], [26], it has also been found to be effective in **Source Separation** problems. In the next chapter we will try to extrapolate what we just explained for that concrete case.

3.4 Diffusion models for Source Separation

In the original paper of diffusion models the noise distribution used for the forward process was “Gaussian Noise”. That means that it is a random distribution with no control of the signal that is being applied to the image. Some time later, researchers found that a **deterministic** signal could be used for the diffusion process, and it would work fine for some concrete applications.

They called this **Cold Diffusion**. The main finding of this paper [25] is that the

generative behaviour of diffusion models is not strongly dependent on the choice of image degradation. In fact, they showcase that different generative models can be modelled using this solution. This approach was already used for speech enhancement when it was found useful for Source Separation.

The Source Separation diffusion inspired strategy implemented by researchers in [27] goes one step forward. As the title says, it is a diffusion “inspired” strategy. This consideration is made because it is not using the generative nature of diffusion models but only the training process. We must note that, if diffusion models were used in a generative way, the source being separated from the mixture should have been generated, not separated. That scenario is not considered in this methodology. In summary, Source Separation using diffusion uses Cold Diffusion with a non-generative approach of diffusion models.

Let’s go deeper in this direction and see how that process is feasible. First, we must know which process is going to be carried out. As we mentioned in the previous section, diffusion works by applying a noise distribution to the data sample. In the Source Separation case, the noise distribution applied to the data sample is the **mixture**. The mixture can be understood as the whole mix of the song from which we want to extract the vocals.

Figure 10: Diffusion process for Source Separation

The vocals are x_0 , and the mixture is added step by step until we arrive to the latent space, which is the complete mixture. The model learns to iteratively retrieve the mixture from the whole song, leaving alone the vocals source and then performing

Source Separation. As it can be noted, this process is totally inspired by diffusion models, but the variables are changed: Gaussian noise is replaced by the mixture, the original image is replaced by the vocals source and the generative nature of the process is replaced by a retrieving process of the sources that must be deleted.

3.5 Diffusion models implementation

In the first sections of this chapter, we discussed our implementation of the neural network, and more specifically the U-net architecture.

The previously theoretically explained diffusion models must be somehow implemented within the architecture itself, in addition to the training process. In this short section we want to detail how the neural network takes this knowledge of the temporal step in which it is located and how we have embedded these elements within the network.

The process is simple. In the end, what the neural network needs most is to know which timestep it is in, so that it can learn to make its way to another timestep. As we will explain in the training section, the main objective of this type of architecture is that it learns to make the path between timesteps, that it learns to automatically move from one to another. For example, if we are in timestep 19, the training process will learn how to move to timestep 18 in the best possible way, it will learn the reverse process in the best possible way. In Figure 11 you can find an embedding space in where similar texts with similar categories are placed in similar parts of the space.

For this purpose, so-called **timestep embeddings** appear. The embeddings are numerical representations of abstract entities in a multidimensional space. This serves, for example, to group elements according to their similarity. This methodology is widely used in NLP (Natural Language Processing) to group semantically similar words.

Extrapolating it to the time domain, these timestep embeddings allow the network to know which time step it is in. Each of these embeddings represents a different

Figure 11: Embedding space example for a NLP task.

timestep. The methodology used is called sinusoidal timestep embeddings, which was first implemented in the famous paper originating from the transformer architecture "Attention is all you need" [50].

Once these embeddings have been generated, all that remains is to add them to the architecture. For this purpose, a small block has been designed consisting of a SiLU non-linearity and a linear layer that allows embeddings to be embedded in each convolutional block of both the encoder and the decoder. It may sound too technical for this document, but the implementation is quite simple, and can be found without any problem in the official repository of this thesis.

Chapter 4

Training

This chapter will be devoted to explaining the training process of the models developed during this thesis. This process is not trivial, especially for the cases in which we use diffusion models, because the training loop has some complicated elements to understand for a person not experienced with deep learning. In this section we will try to explain all these issues in detail.

4.1 Vanilla Unet and Resunet training method

First, we will explain in detail the training strategy followed in the two U-nets developed in this thesis, since both processes are identical. In the creation of a project of this calibre, the recommended methodology for training the model is to create a script dedicated to the construction of the network, where we define the layers, the forward process of the signal throughout the neural network and the different elements that compose it. Once the architecture is finished, the next step is to create the training script, where an instance of the model is created and the training loop is executed. I would like to point out, as a personal opinion, that the training loop is the most complex element of the whole project, as it requires detailed knowledge of all the processes that occur within the neural network and also requires certain knowledge of resource management within the GPU, hyperparameter optimisation and data processing and management.

4.1.1 Data preprocessing

The first step in order to train the model is the preparation of the data. Within the discipline of deep learning, there are areas where data pre-processing consumes the most time in the entire model creation process. This is not exactly the case here, but it does require some work. As discussed in previous sections, one of the limiting elements of any training process is the computational resources available. In this case, and having been quite fortunate, we had access to two NVIDIA T4 graphics cards with 16gb of RAM each. This allowed us to increase the batch size or sample size, but we had to partition the dataset for both the training process and the inference.

The dataset has been divided into 4-second segments. As we have indicated throughout the thesis, the input form of the data to the neural network is in the frequency domain, so therefore, in the form of a spectrogram. For this purpose, we have built what is called a "Data collator", quite common in pytorch, which has allowed us to calculate these spectrograms in windows of 512 samples. Basically, the spectrograms of both the mixture and the vowel signal have been calculated. The data collator made it possible to manage these spectrograms in batch form. This has allowed the network to receive many spectrograms at the same time, randomly during the dataset, which makes the training process much more stable.

4.1.2 Training process

Once the data has been processed, it is time to insert it into the neural network to start the training process. The process, when not using diffusion, is quite simple. Using a type of optimisation commonly called "Adam optimiser", the process is as follows:

1. First define a training data consisting of the mix spectrograms of the batch. Assuming that the batch size is 8, training data is a tensor of 8 tensors containing the information of those 8 mixture spectrograms. This choice is randomised around the training set.

2. At this point, inference is made on the model of all spectrograms in the batch.
3. As a third step, the equivalent ground truth spectrograms are taken, which in this case are the spectrograms of the vowel signal equivalent to each mixture signal, and using the Adam Optimizer, the gradient descent algorithm is performed, calculating the loss value.
4. This process becomes iterative around the complete dataset. When the entire dataset has been completed, which the number of steps will have been the total number of examples divided by the batch size, we have completed an epoch.
5. We repeat the process for a specified number of epochs, i.e. the algorithm iterates around the entire dataset a specified number of times.

This will be discussed later in the evaluation section, but the choice of hyperparameters is often quite decisive in a training process. This is why we have reproduced the process just explained a large number of times in order to find the best possible configuration and thus the best possible model. The hyperparameters include the learning rate, batch size, spectrogram size, hop size, sampling rate and others.

4.2 DiffUnet training method

The part that differs most between the training strategy of the model without diffusion and with diffusion lies in the training loop. It should be noted that the pre-processing of the data is identical, and that the image degradation in the diffusion process is achieved in the training loop.

As discussed above in the theoretical explanation of diffusion, this is where the noise schedule comes into play. This element is a vector that represents the distribution of "noise" around the steps of the diffusion process. Some of them may introduce more noise at the beginning of the process (first steps) while other do the contrary, it depends on the implementation. Let's look at some examples:

1. **Linear Schedule:** This is a straightforward linear increase in the noise level over the steps.

$$\text{noise}[t] = \frac{t}{T}$$

where t is the current step and T is the total number of steps.

2. **Geometric Schedule:** This schedule increases the noise level geometrically over the steps. It's defined by:

$$\text{noise}[t] = (1 - \alpha^{(T-t+1)})$$

where $0 < \alpha < 1$ is a constant factor and T is the total number of steps.

3. **Cosine Schedule:** This schedule uses the cosine function to determine the noise level, providing a smooth curve:

$$\text{noise}[t] = \frac{1 - \cos\left(\pi \cdot \frac{t}{T}\right)}{2}$$

For our final implementation, we decided to use the lineal implementation, as it appears to be the most stable and the most reliable. You can find in Figure 12 how two different noise schedules add noise in a diffusion process.

Figure 12: Linear and cosine noise schedules.

In our training loop, therefore, in order to get what used to be called training data, we have to calculate the noise schedule. Having chosen one, what we must achieve in the training process is that the neural network is able to move from one step to the previous step. As you may recall from the previous explanation, the model must be able to do the reverse process, and for that it needs to learn to go from step 20 to 19, from step 15 to 14, from 12 to 11 or from 1 to 0. To do this, let's say that the training data we have is the spectrogram in the diffusion step we are in (for example step 10) and the target objective, the "ground truth", where we want to go, is the spectrogram in the previous diffusion step, in step 9. This can be clearly visualised in the code of the "trainer.py" attached in the official repository of this thesis.

This training process can be counter-intuitive, but this is how the model learns to finally get from step = t to step = 0, step by step. It is also worth noting that the timesteps at which each batch element is placed differ from each other, causing the model to train in a more stable way.

You may wonder, then, after this explanation, how the model can know in which timestep is located. This is achieved using what is called a timestep embedding. Through a sinusoidal timestep embedding calculation, a 1-D tensor of N indices (N is the batch size) is calculated so the model is aware of the timestep embedding in which is located. That timestep embedding is then embedded into the network at each block, as we explained before in the diffusion strategy implementation section. The embedding is capable of representing in a numerical way something that before deep learning was not possible to represent in a computer.

After this, the model starts training, and some other parameters arise, such as diffusion steps. We must make a compromise between the amount of noise steps and the inference time that we want because inference time is quite important when deploying a model. The standard values used during this training process have been between 8 and 20 steps, taking [27] as reference for that decision.

Chapter 5

Evaluation

The evaluation process is one of the most important processes in any machine learning algorithm. Doing a fair, reliable and quality evaluation means being able to publish the work you have done to the world, and that is what this chapter has tried to do. It is true that it will not be too long, because the evaluation in Music Source Separation is deeply standardised and the number of models to be evaluated is not large. However, we do want to emphasise that the evaluation process has been controlled and reliable, so that the comparison between models is as fair as possible for all of them.

5.1 Metrics

In the realm of source separation, three primary metrics, namely **SDR** (Signal-to-Distortion Ratio), **SIR** (Signal-to-Interference Ratio), and **SAR** (Signal-to-Artifact Ratio), are prevalently utilized for assessing the efficacy of source separation techniques. The concept of measuring signal quality through ratios has been a fundamental aspect of signal processing. The Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR) is one such example that has been used for decades in fields such as telecommunications. These ratios allow for a quantitative comparison between the desired information in a signal and the undesired alterations or distortions.

The application of similar concepts to source separation led to the development of metrics tailored for this purpose:

- **SDR (Signal-to-Distortion Ratio):**

- It quantifies the overall quality of the separated source by juxtaposing the energy of the desired signal against the energy of the errors, encompassing interference, noise, and artifacts.
- Formula:

$$\text{SDR} = 10 \times \log_{10} \left(\frac{\text{Energy of original source}}{\text{Energy of error signal}} \right)$$

- **SIR (Signal-to-Interference Ratio):**

- SIR evaluates the efficacy in the elimination of interference from other sources. This metric contrasts the energy of the desired signal with the energy of the interference.
- Formula:

$$\text{SIR} = 10 \times \log_{10} \left(\frac{\text{Energy of original source}}{\text{Energy of interference}} \right)$$

- **SAR (Signal-to-Artifact Ratio):**

- SAR gauges the paucity of artifacts in the separated source. The energy of the desired signal supplemented by interference is contrasted with the energy of the artifacts.
- Formula:

$$\text{SAR} = 10 \times \log_{10} \left(\frac{\text{Energy of original source plus interference}}{\text{Energy of artifacts}} \right)$$

These indicators can shed light on the strengths and pitfalls of a source separation algorithm. A robust SDR signifies an excellent overall separation, a high SIR reveals

effective interference mitigation, and an elevated SAR indicates a minimal artifact presence in the separated source.

The trio of SDR, SIR, and SAR provides a holistic evaluation framework. While a high SDR might indicate good separation, breaking it down further with SIR and SAR can provide insights into specific areas of improvement. For instance, a good SDR coupled with a low SAR might indicate that while the overall separation is good, the algorithm introduces significant artifacts.

5.2 Evaluation methodology during training process

Training a model for source separation is an intricate process, where the model progressively refines its internal parameters to achieve the desired output. To monitor and ensure the effectiveness of this refinement, it's imperative to periodically evaluate the model's performance. In our study, we have adopted a strategy to assess the model's prowess using SDR metric over a validation set of 4 songs every 5 epochs.

Rationale Behind the Methodology

1. **Monitoring Progress:** Periodic evaluation gives us an opportunity to track the model's learning trajectory. By measuring the SDR at regular intervals, we can visualize how each metric evolves, helping to diagnose potential training issues early.

2. **Avoiding Overfitting:** Evaluating on a validation set distinct from the training set helps in detecting overfitting. If the model performs increasingly well on the training set but deteriorates on the validation set, it's indicative of overfitting. Our periodic evaluations can catch such discrepancies in performance.

3. **Efficient Resource Utilization:** Training deep models can be resource-intensive. By evaluating every 5 epochs, we strike a balance between computational overhead and the frequency of feedback. If the model's performance plateaus or degrades consistently over successive evaluations, early stopping can be considered, saving computational resources.

As it can be noted, we used this process for many reasons, and it has been quite important in time-saving.

5.3 Results

In this section, we unveil the outcomes derived from the evaluation of our different source separation models. Employing the SDR metric, as it shows clearly how the model behaves, we’ve endeavored to provide a comprehensive assessment of the model’s capabilities. These results, captured periodically over the course of the model’s training, shed light on its evolving performance, offering insights into its strengths and potential areas for enhancement.

In the next table we present the results achieved during the process of creation of this thesis. As it can be seen, results are not as good as they could have been expected in some cases. The worst result we had was the Diff Res U-net implementation, which was not capable of achieving more than 2.7 dB, far away from 5.6 dB that [27] achieved in their paper. Nevertheless, the result achieved with Res U-net is quite good. It must not be forgotten that one of the main objectives of this thesis was the implementation **from scratch** of a Source Separation system. Achieving more than 4 dB on a standard benchmark is quite good, and it should be a source of pride.

MODEL	SDR Values on MUSDB Testset
Vanilla U-net	2.5 dB
Res U-net	4.05dB
Diff Res U-net	2.7 dB
WaveNet	4.49dB
Demucs	6.74dB
Diff WaveNet	5.6dB

Chapter 6

Conclusions and further works

In the last section of this thesis, we are going to point out which conclusions we found interesting and worth mentioning, we would like also to discuss the achieved results, the followed methodology and further works that will be done after the presentation of this document.

In the course of this thesis, we embarked on an ambitious journey to introduce a novel approach in the field of Music Source Separation. Building an entire model from scratch is an endeavor fraught with challenges, but it was a necessary step to ensure the purity and uniqueness of our methodology. Our proposed method of diffusion models applied to Music Source Separation in the frequency domain, while innovative, has not yet achieved the levels of quality we aspire to. Nevertheless, the very fact that it operates and has been trained utilizing a completely new method is a testament to its potential.

The complexity of the project was anticipated from the outset. Given the intricacies and the pioneering nature of our work, it's not entirely unexpected that the desired results were not immediately realized. Still, it's essential to understand that this thesis doesn't mark the endpoint but rather serves as a foundation for an entire line of research.

We would like to point some further works that will be done after this thesis. As

we step into the next phase of our research, we are optimistic about refining our model and methodology to achieve the desired results. There are multiple avenues to explore and improve upon our preliminary findings. One promising direction is the integration of FiLM layers to condition the network, which could potentially enhance the network's capability to generalize to more than one source, as the current network works.

Furthermore, with the insights and feedback gathered from this initial attempt, we will be better equipped to identify the areas of improvement and optimize the network accordingly. It's pivotal to remember that innovation often comes with its set of setbacks, but they serve as stepping stones to eventual success.

Finally, as the author of this thesis, I would like to introduce a discussion on why we have not received the results we exactly wanted. There are several possible reasons, but I would like to state two of them, which will be addressed in the future work of this thesis.

Firstly, it is possible that time conditioning is not sufficient for a network as large as this one. It is true that the approach we have used was justified for a much smaller network size than the one we have, so this could be one of the reasons. Another reason is simply that we need a much larger number of steps, which we have not been able to experiment with because of the computational power they require. Both of them will be tested and discussed in future works related to this thesis.

This research has opened doors to numerous possibilities, and we are excited to continue on this path. I personally consider that it has been the chapter of my life that has taught me the most on both a technical level and on the development of agile coding methodologies that have allowed me to be concise and to get to the point in the most important and difficult moments of this journey. We will continue working and improving the work presented in this thesis in order to contribute to the field of Music Source Separation as it deserves.

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